

Scheme 1

Synthesis of some Schiff Bases of 3-Amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones and their Antimicrobial Activities

PRADEEP MISHRA*, P. N. GUPTA and ASHOK K. SHAKYA

Division of Medicinal Chemistry,
Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences.

Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

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COMPOUNDS having quinazolin-4(3H)-one nuclei are reported to show a variety of biological activities¹. Therefore, we have synthesised some Schiff bases of 3-amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones and investigated their antimicrobial properties.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of synthetic grade. Melting points were taken in a Toshniwal apparatus by open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer. Nitrogen estimation was done on a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates using either iodine vapours or KMnO_4 as visualising reagents.

The synthesis followed the sequence as depicted in Scheme 1. 3,5-Dibromoanthranilic acid was synthesised following the reported method².

3-Amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones (2): A mixture of anthranilic acid or 3,5-dibromoanthranilic acid (**1**; 0.05 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.06 mol) was refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 4 h. The excess acetic anhydride was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. The compound so obtained as solid mass was used up immediately for the next step because of its unstable and highly reactive nature.

A mixture of benzoxazin-4-one and hydrazine hydrate (99.5%, 0.1 mol) in dried pyridine was refluxed for 5 h. It was allowed to cool, then poured with stirring in ice-cold distilled water and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The resulting solid was washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol: 3-amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (80%), m.p. 143° (Found: N, 24.15. Calcd. for: 24.00%); ν_{max} 1 680 (N-C=O quinazolinone), 1 610 (C=N), 3 060 (CH aromatic) and 3 550 cm^{-1} (NH of NH_2 group); 3-amino-6,8-dibromo-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (65%), m.p. 134–36° (Found: N, 12.52. Calcd. for: N, 12.59%); ν_{max} 1 670 (N-C=O quinazolinone), 1 615 (C=N), 3 060 (C-H aromatic) and 3 520 cm^{-1} (NH of NH_2 group).

Schiff bases of 3-amino-2-methylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones (3a–r): The carbonyl compound (0.003 mol) was added in small portions to well-stirred warmed clear solution of **2** (0.003 mol) in ethanol containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (~1.0 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 min and then set aside. The resulting solid was washed with dilute alcohol, dried and recrystallised from ethanol-chloroform mixture (2 : 8).

Microbiology: Hi-media bacteriological broth and Hi-media bacteriological nutrient agar for bacteria and Sabouraud dextrose broth and Sabouraud dextrose agar for fungi were used as media. The antimicrobial activities of all compounds were evaluated against some gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*), gram-negative (*Shigella dysenteriae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* O-X-2, and *Shigella flexneri*) bacteria and some fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Micosporum gypseum*) by the filter paper disc agar diffusion

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd no.	X	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
3a	H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	187-9	75
b	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	229-30	58
c	H	H	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	158-60	62
d	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	151-52	66
e	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	174-75	64
f	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (OH)	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	181-87	52
g	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	239-41	60
h	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	185-87	50
i	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂)	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	178-80	64
j	Br	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OBr ₂	184-86	50
k	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (OCH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	163-65	62
l	Br	H	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ OBr ₂	165-67	64
m	Br	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ OBr ₂	163-65	62
n	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂)	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ OBr ₂	170-72	50
o	Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ OBr ₂	182-84	60
p	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (OH)	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	175-77	51
q	Br	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ OBr ₂	192-94	54
r	Br	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ OBr ₂	170-72	45

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

method³. The concentration of the compounds taken was 100 µg ml⁻¹. The results were compared with the standard, i.e. norfloxacin (100 µg ml⁻¹) for antibacterial and clotrimazole (100 µg ml⁻¹) for antifungal studies. All the experiments were carried out in triplicate and the zone of inhibition was measured.

Results and Discussion

In the ir spectra, compounds 3 (Table I), -N-C=O stretch, C=N stretching, C=C and C-H bend vibrations were at the expected values⁴. Moreover, C=N and -N-C=O stretch bands were seen at 1 610 and 1 670 cm⁻¹ respectively belonging to the quinazolinone ring⁵. The disappearance of peak of amino group at 3 500-3 550 cm⁻¹ together with nitrogen analysis confirmed the structures of the compounds.

Out of the compounds evaluated for antibacterial activity, the compounds 3b, c, e, g and h were found to be interesting. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of these compounds was in the range 60-100 µg ml⁻¹. However, none of the compounds were of any significance so far as antifungal activity is concerned.

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